

Perceptions of 2019 Jakarta State University Communication Science Student Towards TikTok Application Users

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Abstract:- The rapid growth of technology continues to bring great changes in human life both in terms of social and culture. The application that will be discussed in this research is the Tik Tok application, which is the latest social media application that allows users to create and various interesting videos. The purpose of this research is to find out the perceptions of UNJ Communication Science students class of 2019 towards the use of the Tik Tok application. The type of research used is descriptive research with a quantitative approach. It can be seen that the benefits of use indicator has the highest average of 3.08%, this shows that the benefits of use indicator on the Perception of Communication Science Students of Jakarta State University 2019 Towards Using the TikTok Application. The conclusion is that students are still accustomed to using other applications so it takes time to adjust. In addition, greater knowledge is needed to dominate the TikTok application in Communication Science UNJ 2019 to make it more interesting and not boring.

Keywords:- Component:- Student Perception, New Media, & Tiktok.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid growth of technology continues to bring great changes in human life both in terms of social and culture. According to (Nuryanto, 2012) The growth of technology in terms of data is so very growing, one of the proofs is that we can easily access data anywhere and anytime with widespread internet networks everywhere, in the source. With the rapid growth of technology, there are various types of social network access that share the convenience of talking to one

another. According to (Nasrullah, 2017) social media invites anyone who is interested to participate by giving donations and feedback openly, giving opinions, and sharing data in a fast and unlimited time.

Social media has earned huge popularity in the last few years and its reach is increasing day by day. Companies believed that it is irresistibly strong medium and a key ingredient for their success. (Roy, 2017) Social media has become a significant necessity in human life today, not only as a place for social interaction and for expanding social networks. The application that will be discussed in this research is the Tik Tok application is the latest social media application that allows users to create and various interesting videos, connect in the opinion column or individual chat. This application introduces special effects that are interesting and easy to use. So that everyone can produce a cool video, this matter makes Tik- Tok as an application with many users.

Tested by the rating obtained from the application's playstore 4, 6 of the best 5 stars and near 27, 827 users worldwide compared to similar applications is Musicaly with a rating of 3, 5 of the best 5 stars after that 4, 100 users. With a large number of users, a positive opinion will arise because of the benefits that the application provides. But on the other hand, the spread of videos with the lack of security of the application makes Tik Tok useless for some, causing an unfavorable opinion of the application.

In research using social assumption theory is referred to as the process of acquiring, understanding, selecting, and organizing sensory data about others. By using social assumption theory, researchers will more easily recognize the extent of Tik Tok users' assumptions through the acquisition

they have, understanding of the Tik Tok application, choosing Tik Tok as the social media they use and organizing data related to the positive and negative values of an application they use by analyzing the source of the factors that influence assumptions.

Students' perceptions are in accordance with the characteristics of elearning learning proposed by (Rusman, 2011), namely:

- **Interactivity:** Availability of additional communication channels, either directly, such as chat or messenger, or indirectly, such as forums, mailing lists, guest books, etc.
- **Independence:** Flexibility in time, location, teacher, and provision of materials. As a result, learning becomes more student-centered.
- **Accessibility:** Access to learning resources is facilitated through online distribution, allowing for broader access compared to the distribution of learning resources in traditional learning.
- **Enrichment:** Learning activities, presentation of lecture materials and training materials as enrichment enable the use of information technology devices such as video streaming, simulations, animations, etc. (Yuniarti, R. & Hartati, 2020)

New media theory is a theory developed by Pierre Levy in his book "Cyberculture" (Levy, 2001), which describes the development of new media from traditional media to digital media. It suggests that it is an explanatory theory. New media, new media is also called digital media. According to Dennis McQuail's book "Mass Communication Theory", the main characteristics of new media are networking, access to individual viewers as receivers and senders of messages, interactivity, plurality as an open character use, and is ubiquitous (Dennis McQuail, 1987).

The term "new media" describes the characteristics of media that are different from their predecessors. Television, magazines, newspapers, radio, newspapers, etc. are classified as old media. Second, Internet media includes interactive properties that are classified as new media. The term new media does not mean that old media has disappeared and become new media. According to Flew, new media are media that encourage digitization, fusion, interactivity, and network development in the context of news production and distribution. New media expertise by encouraging interactivity allows users of new media to choose the information they want to consume. This is a key concept for understanding new media.

New media refers to digital media where all data is processed and stored as numbers and the results are stored on digital media. Digitalization of media has several effects, including dematerialization or separation of text from its physical form. Data is compressed to a smaller size, so you don't need large storage space to store it. Data is fast, easily accessible, and easy to manipulate (Watie, 2011).

TikTok has his POV content trends and perspectives. This is an Indonesian phrase. His POV trend on the TikTok app seems to mimic what Jean Baudrillard called reality. The

POV trend has unwittingly created an unrealistic simulation. The TikTok application is associated with a phenomenon known as hyperreality (Elvira Lisa Baby, Firdaus, Rima Setijowati, 2023). The previous study was titled "Perceptions of Tungadewi University Malang Students on the Use of Tik Tok Application" and the authors were his Demmy Deriyanto and Fathul Qorib. The purpose of this study was to determine how Tribwana University of Tungadewi students' perceptions of using her Tik Tok application are influenced by internal and external factors in forming perceptions. That was it, results of this study.

Findings from a survey on the perceptions of Tribwana Tungadewi University Malang students when using the Tik Tok application, positive perceptions based on the benefits provided and negative perceptions when Tik Tok does not provide benefits to the users announced. Between positive and negative perceptions, there are factors that influence perceptions, both internal and external to the individual user. (Deliyanto and Kollib, 2018).

The purpose of this study was to investigate the perceptions of the Tik Tok application by USU School of Social and Political Science communication studies students in 2015 and 2016, and to determine the effectiveness of the Tik Tok application and to identify factors that influence perceptions of Tik Tok applications among students in communication studies courses in the Department of Social and Political Sciences at USU in 2015 and 2016. According to the survey results, out of 149 students, only 10.1%, or 15 students, use the TikTok application. This indicates that the respondent is not interested in her Tik Tok application.

Furthermore, another study entitled students' perceptions of the use of Tik-Tok as a learning medium. The purpose of this study was to determine the perceptions of students towards the utilization of TikTok as a learning medium. The results of this study indicate that 55.36% of class XI students majoring in Online Business and Marketing at SMKN 1 Makassar liked the utilization of Tiktok as a learning media in the even semester of the 2021 academic year. (Anjani, 2019)

II. RESEARCH METHODS

The type of research used is descriptive research with a quantitative approach. For (Naresh, 2010) descriptive research is a type of research that aims to describe or describe a personality or basic use. The procedure in this research uses survey procedures, for (Naresh, 2010) survey procedures are research procedures using structured questionnaires given to an illustrative population and designed to obtain certain data from respondents. In the survey procedure, the process of collecting and analyzing social information is very structured and detailed through questionnaires as an initial instrument to obtain data from several respondents who are thought to represent a certain population.

The population in this research is an active student of the Communication Science research program at Universitas Negara Jakarta in 2019. The method of taking illustrations in this research is simple random sampling. Simple random

sampling method is one type of probability sampling. Therefore, the number of illustrations in this study was determined using the Slovin formula. Slovin's formula is only used for known populations, because the total population of this research is known to be 82 people, so the Slovin formula can be used as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(df)^2}$$

n = Number of Samples
 N = Total Population
 df = critical value
 n= 82/1+82(0,05)^2
 n=68.049 (rounded to 68)

Based on calculations using the Slovin formula, the number of illustrations in this study were 68 active students of the 2019 State University of Jakarta Communication Science research program.

This research has one research variable, namely perception. In this variable there are 4 measures that have been explained in the introduction above, namely the Interactivity aspect, the Independence aspect, the Accessibility aspect, and the enrichment aspect.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This research has collected some data through distributing questionnaires to predetermined samples. In the questionnaire there are a number of statements made based on indicators of the dimensions of media use. The following is a table of results per indicator:

Table 1. Media Knowledge

Statement	Frequency	Percentage	Average
4= strongly agree	14	20,6%	2,8%
3= agree	35	51,5%	
2= disagree	16	23,5%	
1= strongly disagree	3	4,4%	
Total	68	100%	

The results in the table above show that most respondents answered agree with a percentage of 51.5%, meaning that most of the 2019 UNJ Communication Science students know the TikTok application.

Table 2. User Engagement

Statement	Frequency	Percentage	Average
4= strongly agree	9	13,2%	2,6%
3= agree	30	44,1%	
2= disagree	23	33,8%	
1= strongly disagree	6	8,8%	
Total	68	100%	

The results in the table above show that most respondents answered agree with a percentage of 44.1%, meaning that most of the 2019 UNJ Communication Science students use the TikTok application continuously.

Table 3. Interest in the Content

Statement	Frequency	Percentage	Average
4= strongly agree	12	17,6%	2,75%
3= agree	32	47,1%	
2= disagree	19	27,9%	
1= strongly disagree	5	7,4%	
Total	68	100%	

The results in the table above show that most respondents answered agree with a percentage of 47.1%, meaning that most of the 2019 UNJ Communication Science students like the content in the TikTok application.

Table 4. Message Delivery Media According to the Needs

Statement	Frequency	Percentage	Average
4= strongly agree	10	14,7%	2,8%
3= agree	44	64,7%	
2= disagree	11	16,2%	
1= strongly disagree	3	4,4%	
Total	68	100%	

The results in the table above show that most respondents answered agree with a percentage of 64.7%, meaning that most of the 2019 UNJ Communication Science students use the TikTok application as their need to entertain themselves and fill their spare time.

Table 5. Usage Benefits

Statement	Frequency	Percentage	Average
4= strongly agree	14	20,6%	3,08%
3= agree	48	70,6%	
2= disagree	4	5,9%	
1= strongly disagree	2	2,9%	
Total	68	100%	

The results in the table above show that most respondents answered agree with a percentage of 70.6%, meaning that most of the 2019 UNJ Communication Science students stated that the TikTok application was useful for users to fill their free time.

Table 6. Per Indicator Mean

No	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Knowledge of the media	2,8%
2.	User engagement	2,6%
3.	Interest in the content	2,75%
4.	Message delivery media according to the needs	2,8%
5.	Usage Benefits	3,08%

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the usage benefit indicator has the highest average of 3.08%, this shows that the usage benefit indicator on the Perception of Communication Science Students at Jakarta State University 2019 Towards Using the TikTok Application. Meanwhile, the usage activeness indicator has the lowest average of 2.6%, this means that the usage activeness indicator has the least influence on the Perception of Communication Science Students at Jakarta State University 2019 Towards Using the TikTok Application.

IV. THE CONCLUSION

The perception of 2019 Jakarta State University Communication Science students is quite good towards using the TikTok application, indicated by student knowledge of using the TikTok application which is classified as moderate (51.1%). The benefits of use are in a fairly high category (70.6%). However, the activeness of use is low, 44.1% of students stated that they do not always use the TikTok application as a free time filler. The low number of these students results in the frequent use of Communication Science students at UNJ 2019 choosing other applications. Students are still accustomed to using other applications so it takes time to adjust. In addition, greater knowledge is needed to dominate the TikTok application in Communication Science UNJ 2019 to make it more interesting and not boring.

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